

WAYS TO APPLY TECHNICAL METHODS OF PEDAGOGY OF SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING IN THE EFFECTIVE TRAINING OF SPECIAL FORCES SOLDIERS

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Abstract: In this paper we describe the aspects of mining collective action the arrest of criminals on the lessons of physical training. Offer some methodological techniques when working in «pairs of combat and combat threes», that allows to solve operatively-service problems quickly and with maximum efficiency without additional application of physical force and special means.

Keywords: Staff training, battle stance, the methods of physical training, special events, group of special purpose, martial pair, martial Troika.

1 INTRODUCTION

The criminalization of modern society and, as a consequence, the high level of crime in the country places increased demands on the activities of various services, including the professional training of the employees themselves for effective actions in normal and especially extreme situations [1, p. 52].

The functioning of special-purpose units in the system of the Republic of Uzbekistan at this point in time is an objective need to prevent and suppress offenses by force.

Due to the fact that the use of special-purpose departments is often the last argument in resolving a crisis situation, SPECIAL UNIT employees must have high professional training and have good physical, psychological, moral and intellectual qualities and abilities.

Combat training of personnel SPECIAL UNIT due to the specifics of the functions performed, in our opinion, represents a special area of activity and significance in the system of professional training of employees of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This unit is a special structure that solves particularly important tasks, where the success of the operation depends on the physical, combat and psychological readiness of each individual.

2 REFORMS FOR IMPROVING PHYSICAL FITNESS

The training program for employees of the SPECIAL DIVISION of territorial bodies Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated

December 10, 2021 No. PQ-40 “On additional measures to ensure a high level of physical fitness of military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan” determines that the training of a special unit employee is aimed at ensuring his constant combat readiness, the formation of high professional, moral, psychological and combat qualities that allow timely and high-quality execution of assigned service and combat missions in difficult operational conditions. The same program classifies physical training as a special subdivisional subject of training for personnel SPECIAL UNIT, along with combined arms tactics, special tactical and fire training.

It is known that the actions of employees under unfavorable conditions, for example, during special events in correctional colonies (confrontations with aggressive crowds), lengthy search, prosecution and detention of criminals, the need to suppress offenses by force, cause changes in the functional state of the body, which sometimes leads to deterioration of professional performance indicators. In order to compensate for these negative phenomena in the classroom, it is necessary to simulate probable situations of service and combat activity using means and methods of physical training.

In our article, we would like to touch upon some aspects of practicing collective actions during the detention of criminals in physical training classes.

Collective coordinated work is a special subunit tactic of any special forces, but it is especially important for the special forces of the penal system, because The

usual ratio of offender / officer SPECIAL UNIT when conducting special events in correctional colonies is 10-20/1. Working in “combat pairs” and “combat trios” allows you to solve operational tasks quickly and with maximum efficiency without the additional use of special equipment. It is known that any crowd is a community of individuals, although united by common interests, but lacking sufficient coherence and communication. And the “combat duo” of special forces employees is a single organism, acting according to the same plan and capable of transforming depending on the developing operational situation.

In this work, we will reveal only special subdivisional principles, without touching on the technique of working as a “combat team” during special events.

3 RECOMMENDED METHODS OF ORGANIZING PHYSICAL FITNESS

The special subdivisional task of employees working in the “combat duo” system against numerically superior intruders is to create, at least for a short time, overwhelming superiority in a separate section of the “front.” This is achieved primarily by maneuver and coordinated attack at different levels. Depending on the tactical situation, suppression of enemy resistance can be with the help of impact, shock-throw suppression, and impact with throws with the transition to escort techniques. With a coordinated paired attack, the enemy physically will not be able to provide significant resistance, especially if the attack is carried out at different levels and with constant switching from striking to throwing influence. To improve work in the “fighting duo” in physical training classes, it is possible to use the following leading exercises and methodological techniques:

- “copying”: employees take a combat stance, in assault order (the first number is in front, the second 1-1.5 meters behind and slightly to the side). The first number performs shadow boxing, the second copies all his movements. Due to the complexity of the task, you should start by copying movements at a slow pace, gradually increasing the speed, adding punches and kicks, simulating throws;

- “carousel”: alternating strike attack on one opponent or on a boxing bag with movement in a circle. The first one attacks - the second one ensures his safety from behind;

- “tag in pairs”: employees are divided into pairs and play a two-on-two battle. Task: quickly and easily touch the opponent’s shoulders, stomach or thighs, while trying to create a temporary two-on-one superiority;

- “attack by sector”: employees can develop a simultaneous attack effect by sector either on punching bags, or in threes, where one plays the criminal. Employees in a combat stance, in assault order, at the command of the first number (the senior in the pair), each begin to strike at their half of the target (the target is conventionally divided by an axial vertical line into the left and right sectors of the attack). Task: simultaneous start and simultaneous end of the attack, while carrying out the attack, do not interfere with the actions of the partner. The trajectories of strikes and other actions of the first and second numbers do not intersect with each other. The blows occur simultaneously, with different frequencies, at different levels, with different strengths.

- “attack by levels”: the target is conventionally divided by a horizontal line into upper and lower levels. Employees in a combat stance, in assault order, at the command of the first number (the eldest in the pair), carry out an attack: the first number is the head, upper level, the second number is the legs, lower level. The task of the first is to force the enemy to protect his head, to fetter the actions of the enemy’s hands, and to create favorable conditions for the actions of the second number. The task of the second, attacking the legs and lower level, is to transfer the opponent to the ground and, without allowing him to take the “embryo” pose, give the first number the opportunity to move to bend his arm behind his back;

- “wave”: Employees in a combat stance, in assault formation, at the command of the first number (the eldest in the pair) attack the target. First, there is a shock attack of the first number on the upper level and after which he goes into a grip on the lower level, in order to transfer the enemy to a position on the ground, and the second number covers the upper level of the enemy with a second wave of impact, providing freedom of action for the first number on the lower level.

- Also, to increase the level of preparedness of assault group employees during physical training classes, you can use the game method, simulating the specifics of the actions of special forces during special operations. First of all, it is the ability to work in a crowd. To develop this skill, you can use the following techniques:

- simultaneous group game of tag in the ring (or in any limited area);

- a basketball game with the ability to capture any player from the enemy team;

- a game of football with the ability to capture the player holding the ball, etc.

Systematic conduct of classes, repeated repetition of the learned techniques in various combinations and in a variety of settings helps to consolidate the strength of acquired skills, develop physical qualities in employees and cultivate moral and volitional qualities [3, p. 35].

4 CONCLUSIONS

We believe that it is effective to conduct training by taking into account complex, real situations and targeting the formation of skills, increasing the qualities of speed, strength and endurance. As we see, the means and methods of physical training make it possible to sufficiently effectively increase the level of combat training of employees of assault groups SPECIAL UNIT of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This can be attributed to both the individual preparedness of employees and the group coherence of the unit in solving operational and service tasks.

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